

Extended Data: Interview Guide and Informed Consent (PATTERN Task 1.1)

Project: PATTERN – Piloting open and responsible Activities and Trainings Towards the Enhancement of Researchers Networks

Work Package: WP1

Task: Task 1.1 – Mapping and analysis of training activities

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Ethics approval: Aarhus University Research Ethics Committee (Approval no. 2023-001)

Project context

These interviews were conducted as part of Task 1.1 within Work Package 1 of the PATTERN project. The objective was to map and analyse existing training resources in Open and Responsible Research and Innovation (Open RRI). The interviews complemented desk research, surveys, and workshops by providing expert perspectives on training provision, quality, gaps, and needs.

Informed consent

You are invited to participate in an interview on learning opportunities for researchers regarding Open and Responsible Research and Innovation (Open RRI). You have been selected based on your expertise.

The interview will take approximately 30 minutes and will be recorded and transcribed. Personally identifiable information will be removed and replaced with pseudonyms.

Participation is voluntary. You may withdraw at any time without consequence, and your data will be deleted upon request.

The data will be used for research purposes within the PATTERN project and may be included in publications in pseudonymised form. Data will be stored securely for up to five years.

This study has been approved by the Aarhus University Research Ethics Committee (Approval no. 2023-001).

Interview guide

Introductory questions

- How do you view Open RRI? How important is it for society and researchers?
- How far has the Open RRI transformation progressed?
- What mechanisms support Open RRI in your institution?

Training provision

- What types of training in Open RRI are offered by your institution?
- Can you provide details (duration, format, audience)?
- What is the uptake and feedback?

Gaps and needs

- What are the most important gaps in Open RRI training?
- Are there differences across career stages or regions?

Training quality and good practices

- What does high-quality training look like?
- Can you provide examples of good practice?

Impact and evaluation

- How do researchers apply learnings in practice?
- How can training impact be evaluated?